

Electrochemical sensing of perfluorooctanoic acid in wastewater: Characterization of a molecularly imprinted polymer-based sensor

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ABSTRACT

Stricter guidelines are progressively established to control the presence of perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) in water bodies due to its toxicity and persistence in the environment. This study focused on the development of an electrochemical sensor based on a molecularly imprinted poly(*o*-phenylenediamine) film to detect PFOA in aqueous matrices. A comparative evaluation of sensor fabrication and analytical performance was performed on gold (AuE) and glassy carbon (GCE) electrodes. Experimental conditions influencing electropolymerization behavior, template removal, polymer morphology, and PFOA recognition were studied. Characterizations using electrochemical techniques and Raman spectroscopy were correlated with analytical performance. These were assessed in spiked buffer solution, yielding concentration-dependent trends over a wide dynamic range, with detection limits of 23.0 and 20.2 ppt for the AuE and the GCE, respectively, meeting the sensitivity requirements of current EU regulations. Selectivity was evaluated by studying sensor response in the co-presence of potential interferences. The sensor was then tested on real samples collected from a wastewater treatment plant. A minor matrix effect was registered in the filtered effluent, supporting the applicability of the sensor for rapid on-site PFOA screening near regulatory thresholds.

1. Introduction

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are a vast class of synthetic organic compounds widely used across various industries, including aerospace, chemical manufacturing, electroplating, electronics, and food packaging (Glüge et al., 2020; Giesy and Kannan, 2002). Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) and perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS) are two of the most extensively studied, as well as the most dangerous and toxic non-polymeric PFAS compounds for the environment and human beings (Wee and Aris, 2023; Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic, 2023; Lohmann and Letcher, 2023; van Gerwen et al., 2023; Li et al., 2025). These conditions have prompted regulatory bodies worldwide to establish increasingly stringent laws and guidelines to regulate their presence in environmental matrices. In Europe, regarding PFAS in drinking water, the relevant document is the EU Directive 2020/2184, which defines chemical parameters, including concentration limits for “Total PFAS” (the totality of per- and

polyfluoroalkyl substances) and the “Sum of PFAS” (a subset of “Total PFAS” that includes substances hazardous to water intended for human consumption). Specifically, the “Total PFAS” value must not exceed a threshold of 0.50 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, while the “Sum of PFAS”—which includes substances such as PFOA, PFOS, and perfluorobutanoic acid (PFBA)—must not exceed 0.10 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (Official Journal of the European Union, 2020).

In this context, an accurate, sensitive, but simple strategy to determine PFOA is of paramount importance. To provide safer water sources, it is crucial to understand the occurrence and fate of PFOA in wastewater treatment plants, in order to embrace timely interventions when limits exceed fixed thresholds and develop effective removal and mitigation strategies. Currently, the gold standard for the quantitative analysis of PFAS heavily relies on hyphenated chromatographic techniques, primarily (ultra)high-performance liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS/MS) (Thompson et al., 2024). However, when approaching decentralized contexts, it is often more

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useful to perform screening analyses using alternative rapid analytical strategies to identify and detect specific analytes in a sample, following simple sample pre-treatment procedures (Thompson et al., 2024). Recently, the attention has shifted toward electrochemical sensors, due to their advantages, including ease of use, rapid response, and suitability for *in situ* analysis. Considering the inherent electrochemical inactivity of PFAS within typical experimental conditions (Costa et al., 2023; Kazemi et al., 2020), selective recognition elements are usually employed in the sensing scheme to recognize the analyte and generate a measurable signal. Although widely used in sensing applications, biological recognition elements – like antibodies – against PFAS can be challenging to produce, as PFAS may not be (sufficiently) immunogenic to elicit a strong immune response (Blinc et al., 2024; Barton et al., 2022). Furthermore, bioreceptors are often very sensitive to harsh environmental conditions, such as pH levels and organic solvents, which may be present in real samples or required for sensor regeneration. In this context, molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs) coupled to electrochemical sensors provide an attractive and cheaper alternative as synthetic biomimetic receptors and have recently been reported in the literature for the detection of PFAS, including PFOS and PFOA (Ahmadi Tabar et al., 2023). Although not completely immune to harsh conditions, MIPs are generally considered more resistant to organic solvents, extreme pH, and thermal treatments than biological counterparts (Elugoke et al., 2021; Parisi et al., 2022). Electrochemical MIP-based approaches usually focus on the template-assisted electropolymerization of monomers directly onto the electrode surface. In the case of PFAS, *ortho*-phenylenediamine (*o*-PD) appears to be the most frequently used monomer for the synthesis of MIPs. The rebinding of the target causes a concentration-dependent signal-off behavior, allowing for the indirect quantification of PFAS (Lamichhane and Arrigan, 2023). However, most reports leave unclear how much the electrode surface truly steers the final analytical performances once a non-conductive imprinted layer controls interfacial transport and recognition. Recent review papers (Thompson et al., 2024; Lamichhane and Arrigan, 2023; Liang et al., 2025) and studies report on conductive/redox-active MIP films (Hafeez et al., 2024), MIP nanoparticles (Costa et al., 2023), nanomaterials, or other complex electrode surface functionalizations and nanostructurations (Wei et al., 2023; Rehman et al., 2024; Kamel et al., 2024) to achieve ppb to sub-ppt PFAS detection limits. Furthermore, many works in the literature indeed underscore feasibility, but do not systematically test whether intrinsic electron transfer kinetics actually translate into tangible analytical gains over simpler electrode designs under matched protocols. While gold disk and glassy carbon electrodes are the most widely employed, screen-printed platforms coupled with MIPs have also been attempted for PFAS sensing (Tabar et al., 2025). However, in some cases, surface imaging studies revealed morphology-driven heterogeneity in the polymer distribution within the MIP layer, which was qualitatively associated with reproducibility challenges (Moro et al., 2019). Indeed, combinations of MIPs with nanostructures, like gold nanoparticles (Gao et al., 2023) or carbon nanowalls (Pierpaoli et al., 2023), often enhance electrochemical performances, but the link between these improvements and stronger analytical performance is very rarely compared head-to-head against simpler/unmodified counterparts under identical conditions. These gaps point to a question: does pushing electrode interfacial electron-transfer kinetics or nanostructuring consistently pay off when a non-conductive imprinted film governs mediator access and binding, or do simpler/bare substrates already provide the performances required to reach regulatory ranges for PFAS when the MIP layer is optimized? In this context, the present work explicitly compares the two most common electrode materials used in this field, namely gold and glassy carbon, under unified fabrication and measurement workflows to test whether potential differences in electrochemical properties significantly shift PFOA detection limits of an electrochemical sensor once a molecularly imprinted poly(*o*-phenylenediamine) film controls recognition and electron transfer at the interface. Electrochemical and Raman

spectroscopy characterizations were carried out before and after polymerization and imprinting to better understand differences in polymer formation, template removal, mediator access, and PFOA binding behavior on both gold (AuE) and glassy carbon (GCE) electrodes. After introducing a number of optimizations and studying potential interfering molecules, the more promising setup was used to investigate the sensor's behavior in real samples collected from a wastewater treatment plant. Indeed, while many studies on PFAS demonstrate sensor performance in different or relatively clean matrices, like buffer solutions, tap water, surface water, or sea/river water (Gao et al., 2023; Karimian et al., 2018; Clark and Dick, 2020; Lu et al., 2022), fewer test directly wastewater samples. To the best of our knowledge, no other works have been reported in the literature comparing the performance of gold and glassy carbon surfaces modified with a poly(*o*-PD) imprinted layer for the detection of PFOA under identical workflows and studying the sensor's behavior in wastewater.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Chemicals and materials

Ferrocenecarboxylic acid (FcCOOH, $\geq 96\%$), *o*-phenylenediamine (*o*-PD, 99.5%), perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA, 95%), methanol (for high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), $\geq 99\%$), ammonia solution (NH₃, 25%), sodium acetate trihydrate (CH₃COONa•3H₂O), acetic acid (CH₃COOH), ammonium chloride (NH₄Cl), potassium chloride (KCl), potassium hexacyanoferrate (II/III) (K₄[Fe(CN)₆]/K₃[Fe(CN)₆]), hydroquinone (HQ, $\geq 99\%$), Amoxicillin (AMX, by USP®), and Aroclor 1242 mixture in isooctane (Supelco) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Milan, Italy). Lead ICP standard solution (Pb²⁺) was purchased from Fisher Scientific (Milan, Italy). All purchased reagents were used as received, without further purification. Wastewater samples were collected from a local wastewater treatment plant, as reported in the following sections.

Aqueous solutions were prepared using water treated with the Milli-Q Water Purification System (Millipore, UK), characterized by a resistivity of 18.2 MΩ cm. Two main buffer solutions were used: (i) 0.1 M acetate buffer pH 5.8 was obtained by mixing 94.1 mM of CH₃COONa•3H₂O and 5.9 mM of CH₃COOH in Milli-Q Water; (ii) 0.01 M ammonia buffer pH 8.4 consisted of 0.01 M NH₄Cl, 0.01 M NH₃, and 0.1 M KCl in Milli-Q Water. Two redox mediators were tested for the electrochemical measurements: a 5 mM [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} solution, prepared by dissolving 2.5 mM K₄[Fe(CN)₆] and 2.5 mM K₃[Fe(CN)₆] in ammonia buffer pH 8.4, and a 0.5 mM FcCOOH solution in ammonia buffer pH 8.4.

Mixing of the solutions was achieved by vortexing (TK3S, TechnoKartell) or magnetic stirring (TK22, TechnoKartell). The PK-4 Polishing Kit from BASi (USA) was used for the polishing treatment of the electrodes, as described in the following sections.

2.2. Apparatus

A 5 mL glass beaker was employed as the electrochemical cell, filled with 3 mL of sample/solution. The working electrode consisted of either a gold disk (Ø 1 mm) or a glassy carbon electrode (Ø 5 mm), both interfaced to an Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) reference electrode and a platinum counter electrode. The working electrodes were produced in house as reported in details elsewhere (Palleschi et al., 1989). The electrodes were immersed directly into the solution, maintaining a conventional three-electrode system. This setup was consistently used for electropolymerization steps, buffer-based calibrations, and tests with real wastewater samples. All experiments were conducted under ambient atmosphere, following protocols already established in the literature (Wei et al., 2023; Clark and Dick, 2020; Lu et al., 2022). The absence of deaeration steps was motivated by efforts to keep the protocol straightforward and suitable for field-ready sensor deployment. All

potentials reported in this work are referred to the Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) reference electrode. Electrochemical measurements were conducted using the portable potentiostat PalmSens4 (PalmSens BV, Utrecht, The Netherlands), remotely controlled via Bluetooth® through the PStTrace 5.11 software (PalmSens BV, Utrecht, The Netherlands). Data analysis was performed using Origin Pro 2025 (OriginLab Corporation).

Polymer morphology and template removal were studied by collecting Raman spectra with a Renishaw inVia™ Qontor® confocal Raman microscope (Renishaw plc, Gloucestershire, UK) equipped with a Leica DM microscope. The excitation source was a 532 nm laser line (diode-type, 80 mW, 1800 lines/mm grating). Laser focusing on the electrode surface was achieved through a 50LX objective (NA 0.50, WD 8.20 mm), following instrument calibration on the internal silicon reference standard ($520.5 \pm 0.1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Spectra were acquired in static mode with a spectral resolution of 1 cm^{-1} , covering a spectral range between 100 and 3200 cm^{-1} . Data processing was performed using Renishaw WIRE software (version 3.2).

2.3. MIP/NIP sensor preparation

Before each electropolymerization step, the working electrodes underwent a physical cleaning phase to homogenize the electrode surface and remove undesired adsorbed material (Pellittero et al., 2025; Bettazzi et al., 2018). Particularly, the gold disk electrode was polished by scrubbing the gold surface for 2 min following an “8-shape”-like movement first with an ultrafine diamond polish with a grit size of $1 \mu\text{m}$, followed by rinsing with methanol and Milli-Q water and by 2 more minutes on wet $0.05 \mu\text{m}$ alumina slurry. The debris formed was then removed by sonicating the electrodes for 2 min in distilled water. The gold electrode was then electrochemically activated. This step consisted of 200 cyclic voltammetry (CV) scans in $0.5 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ in a potential window from $+0.4 \text{ V}$ to $+1.7 \text{ V}$ at a scan rate of 0.5 V s^{-1} . Instead, the glassy carbon electrode was polished with a $0.05 \mu\text{m}$ alumina polish solution and sonicated in distilled water for 2 min.

The electrosynthesis of the molecularly imprinted poly(*o*-PD) was achieved by 25 CV scans in the potential range from 0.0 V to $+1.0 \text{ V}$ at the scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} in a solution of acetate buffer pH 5.8 and methanol 2:1 (v/v) containing either 10 mM o-PD alone (for the non-imprinted polymer, NIP) or with the addition of 1 mM PFOA (for the

molecularly imprinted polymer, MIP). PFOA and *o*-PD solutions were freshly prepared before each electropolymerization. No deaeration phases, such as inert-gas purging, were performed prior to or during the electropolymerization step. Template removal was achieved by keeping the modified working electrodes in methanol under mild magnetic stirring for 20 min. The electrodes were then dried under air flow and stored in a clean container at room temperature to prevent particulate contamination until use. Fig. 1 briefly schematizes the strategy described.

2.4. Electrochemical characterization and PFOA detection

Before PFOA detection, the electrodes were characterized electrochemically using cyclic voltammetry with redox indicators. Unless stated otherwise, the characterization was performed in a potential range between -0.1 V and $+0.5 \text{ V}$ at a varying scan rate between 10 and 100 mV s^{-1} (for the blank sample, the potential was swept at 25 mV s^{-1}). The Randles–Ševčík equation reported below was used to study the relationship between the anodic and cathodic peak currents with $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$ solutions and the square root of the scan rate used in cyclic voltammetry. Moreover, the same equation allowed us to estimate the electrochemically active area of each electrode surface through other parameters such as the number of electrons exchanged (n), the diffusion coefficient (D , in $\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$), the concentration of the redox indicator (C , in mol cm^{-3}), the scan rate (ν , in V s^{-1}), and the anodic or cathodic current peaks measured by CV (i_p , in A). More information on this equation can be found elsewhere (Sfragano et al., 2024a).

$$i_p = 2.686 \cdot 10^5 \cdot z^2 \cdot A \cdot D^{\frac{1}{2}} \cdot C \cdot \nu^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

The electrochemically active area of the AuE was $0.025 \pm 0.001 \text{ cm}^2$, whereas that of the GCE was $0.369 \pm 0.030 \text{ cm}^2$. This is in line with a 5-fold difference between the two electrodes' nominal diameters ($\varnothing 1 \text{ mm}$ for the AuE and $\varnothing 5 \text{ mm}$ for the GCE). Indeed, this disparity naturally resulted in higher absolute peak currents for the GCE compared to the AuE under identical concentration and scan rate conditions. Notably, upon normalizing current values for the electrochemically active area, the resulting (peak) current densities were comparable between the two electrodes at a given scan rate. This implies that, once the effective

Fig. 1. Schematic protocol for the proposed PFOA detection strategy. The MIP layer is electrosynthesized *in situ* over the electrode surface in the presence of the monomer, *o*-phenylenediamine (*o*-PD), and the template molecule, perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA). Template removal is achieved by keeping the electrode in methanol under mild stirring. Upon interaction with the sample, the PFOA contained therein starts to occupy the imprinted cavities. After adding ferrocenecarboxylic acid (FcCOOH), the voltammetric readout registers a decrease in current peak intensity (or an increase in $\Delta I_p / I_{p0}$) proportionate to the concentration of PFOA in the sample. The electrode can then be reused either by performing a new template removal or by electropolymerizing fresh *o*-PD after cleaning the electrode surface.

surface area available for the reaction is considered, the intrinsic rate of electron transfer per unit area is similar for the two materials and that the capacity of each electrochemically active site to facilitate the charge transfer of the redox mediator is comparable on both surfaces. Thus, to better compare the results obtained, the data in this paper are reported considering current density or current density peaks (J or J_p , respectively) instead of the current intensity values. More in detail, cyclic voltammograms are reported as J values vs. the potential (E). Furthermore, two voltammetric techniques with complementary electrochemical advantages, namely differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) and square-wave voltammetry (SWV), were tested under identical experimental conditions for the determination of PFOA. After the preparation of the sensor, including electropolymerization and template removal phases, the electrode was used to determine PFOA concentration in samples. Specifically, the electrode was subjected to a 15 min incubation time under magnetic stirring inside the sample, followed by voltammetric measurements (DPV or SWV) in ammonia buffer pH 8.4 containing 0.5 mM FcCOOH in a potential window between 0.0 V and +0.6 V. The following parameters were used for DPV: step potential of 4 mV, pulse amplitude of 25 mV, pulse width of 25 ms, and scan rate of 20 mV s⁻¹. Likewise, for SWV, the parameters were set to comprise a step potential of 10 mV, a pulse amplitude of 50 mV, and a frequency of 5 Hz. FcCOOH solutions were freshly prepared before each use. No deaeration procedures (i.e., inert gas purging) were carried out before or during the interaction with the sample or the electrochemical measurements. The interaction with PFOA was evaluated considering the normalized reduction in peak current density caused by PFOA binding against the initial signal ($\Delta J_p/J_{p0}$). This value was calculated as a % ratio, where ΔJ_p represents the peak current density registered for the blank sample in the absence of PFOA (J_{p0}) subtracted from the corresponding current density observed in the sample under analysis. This normalization helps to compare results obtained from different sensors, as it helps to account for variability between individual fabricated sensors. Scatchard analysis and data fitting with the Langmuir-Freundlich isotherm were performed as reported elsewhere (Kazemi et al., 2020; Pesavento et al., 2019). The limit of detection (LOD) and the limit of quantification (LOQ) were evaluated by considering the average signal of the blank sample augmented by three (LOD) or ten (LOQ) times its standard deviation. The values obtained were then converted into concentrations by fitting to the calibration function (Sfragano et al., 2024b).

2.5. Real wastewater samples

Wastewater samples were obtained from a local wastewater treatment plant, collecting both (i) water samples before entering the plant, thus downstream of all water reclamation processes, and (ii) the outgoing effluent after the treatment. Right after collection, these samples were stabilized at pH 1.0 by adding concentrated HNO₃. Once received at the lab for the analyses, they were stored at +4 °C in the dark until use (max 7 days). Before the analysis, wastewater samples were added of a small volume of 0.3 M ammonia buffer to adjust electrolyte concentrations and final pH in order to recreate similar conditions to those of the standard buffer solutions analyzed (i.e., pH 8.4). These samples were either analyzed as mentioned, without further purification steps, or after filtration through a sterile polyethersulfone (PES) membrane with a pore size of 0.45 μm (Sarstedt AG & Co., Italy) to remove impurities and particulate matter that may hamper the measurements. Matrix effect (%) was evaluated by comparing the signals obtained in spiked wastewater with those registered in the buffer, as reported elsewhere (Moro et al., 2022).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Electrochemical characterization of AuE and GCE

In this work, the behavior of two different electrode materials was

tested upon modifying the surface with MIPs to make them sensitive for the detection of PFOA. At first, the bare gold and glassy carbon electrode surfaces were electrochemically characterized. Thus, CV scans were registered in 0.1 M KCl in the absence (blank) or presence of 5 mM [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-}, in a potential range from -0.1 V to +0.5 V at a varying scan rate from 10 mV s⁻¹ to 100 mV s⁻¹. As expected, cyclic voltammograms (Fig. 2a) recorded in 0.1 M KCl alone show no faradaic contributions to the current, confirming the absence of electroactive species on both electrode surfaces potentially hampering the voltammetric analyses in the potential range investigated (Sfragano et al., 2022). Then, a comparison of the cyclic voltammograms obtained with AuE and GCE across a range of scan rates revealed distinct electrochemical behavior. With the AuE, at 25 mV s⁻¹, an anodic peak around +0.26 V (E_{pa}) and a cathodic peak (E_{pc}) around +0.17 V can be observed for the one-electron transfer process associated with the Fe(II)/Fe(III) redox couple, accounting for a peak-to-peak potential difference ($\Delta E = |E_{pa} - E_{pc}|$) of 90 mV at the scan rate of 25 mV s⁻¹. This confirms a good reversibility of the redox indicator, further corroborated by a value for the anodic-to-cathodic peak currents ratio ($|i_a/i_c|$) close to unity (1.07) as for ideally reversible processes. The analysis of the relationship between the anodic (J_{pa}) and cathodic (J_{pc}) peak current densities and the square root of the scan rate ($v^{1/2}$) demonstrated a generally linear trend ($R^2 = 0.994 \pm 0.001$) for the AuE. This indicates that the reaction rate of the observed processes is governed by the diffusion of the redox species from the bulk solution to the electrode surface, as described by the Randles-Ševčík equation. In the case of GCE, for the [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-}, at 25 mV s⁻¹, the anodic peak falls at a potential of +0.29 V, while the cathodic one is found at +0.15 V, thus indicating a higher ΔE value (140 mV) compared to the AuE, sign of larger kinetic barrier for charge transfer across the electrode-solution interface. Likewise, the $|i_a/i_c|$ slightly worsens, with a value of 1.13, further supporting the conclusion that the [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-}/[Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻ redox reaction approaches reversible behavior more closely on the gold electrode surface compared to the glassy carbon one. Regarding the relationship between J_{pa} and J_{pc} with $v^{1/2}$, although a linear trend is still observable, the coefficient of determination was marginally lower for the GCE (0.988 ± 0.006) compared to the AuE, indicating a rate of charge transfer not infinitely fast relative to the rate of diffusion (Sfragano et al., 2024a). The data, visually summarized in Fig. 2b, suggest ferro-ferricyanide quasi-reversible behaviors on both electrode surfaces, while also indicating that the reversibility of the Fe(II)/Fe(III) couple is enhanced on the gold surface and that faster electron transfer kinetics happen at the AuE, thus indicating better electrochemical performance at this latter electrode (Bettazzi et al., 2021). Indeed, these intrinsic electrochemical properties might exert a potential influence on the performance of the resulting MIP-based sensors when used to detect PFOA.

3.2. Differences in the o-PD electropolymerization process

The electrosynthesis of the polymeric film of o-PD on both AuE and GCE was achieved through repeated CV scans for 25 consecutive cycles at pH 5.8 with 10 mM o-PD, both in the presence of 1 mM PFOA as the template molecule (MIP) or in its absence (NIP). A monomer:template molar ratio of 10:1 was used (Karimian et al., 2018). The resulting voltammetric profiles are illustrated in Fig. 3 as J (μA cm⁻²) vs. E (V). With both electrodes, the initial voltammogram displayed distinct oxidation peaks related to o-PD, primarily attributable to the oxidation of the amine groups that characterize the monomer structure (Losito et al., 2001; Tricase et al., 2024). Particularly, for the AuE-MIP sensor, an oxidation peak appears around +0.42 V with a shoulder around +0.64 V. In the corresponding AuE-NIP, the two peaks are negligibly shifted at +0.43 V and +0.72 V, respectively. Similarly, on the GCE-MIP, o-PD oxidation peaks are observed at +0.54 V and +0.76 V, whereas the GCE-NIP voltammograms show two well-defined peaks at +0.54 V and +0.81 V. In all cases, no cathodic peaks were detected. With the progressive increase in the number of CV scans, starting already with the

Fig. 2. (a) Cyclic voltammograms in 0.1 M KCl in the absence (blank) or presence of 5 mM $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$ at unmodified gold (left) and glassy carbon (right) electrodes. The insets show the anodic (full squares, $J_{p,a}$) and cathodic (empty squares, $J_{p,c}$) current peak densities (J_p) as a function of the square root of the scan rate (v). (b) Data extracted from CV scans at 25 mV s^{-1} at both electrodes in 0.1 M KCl added with 5 mM $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$, including anodic ($J_{p,a}$) and cathodic ($J_{p,c}$) peak current densities, electroactive areas, peak-to-peak potential differences (ΔE) and anodic-to-cathodic peak current ratio ($|i_a/i_c|$). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

second one, a significant decrease in the overall current measured was observed, eventually yielding relatively flat voltammetric profiles. This trend is consistent with the formation of a non-conductive (or scarcely conductive) *o*-PD film over the surface of the electrode, which progressively hinders electron transfer at the electrode-solution interface. It is interesting to observe that, in the NIP voltammograms, the oxidation peaks – especially those at more positive potentials – are more pronounced and better defined than those of the MIP. This is in line with previous studies (Lu et al., 2022) that found that the addition of the template molecule led to the reduction or the near disappearance of the second oxidation peak of *o*-PD. Notably, this documented effect on the second peak was exploited in literature-reported cases as the direct proof of the incorporation of the template molecule inside the polymeric layer (Karimian et al., 2018; Lu et al., 2022; Suryanarayanan et al., 2010). In this context, the MIP voltammograms reported in Fig. 3 show that the second oxidation peak of *o*-PD appeared less defined and resolved in the case of the GCE when compared to that recorded at the AuE. Considering what was stated above, this aspect could potentially imply that more PFOA molecules got entrapped in the polymeric layer on the GCE.

It is interesting to highlight that, during the electropolymerization process with the GCE, flatter voltammograms are observable during the last CV scans compared to those registered at the AuE, as evidenced by the red dashed curves in Fig. 3 after the normalization for geometric area differences between the two electrode surfaces. This superior passivation observed on the GCE could imply a more uniform and complete polymer formation of the poly(*o*-PD) film (Abo-Elmagd et al., 2021). Furthermore, using both electrode materials, the MIP voltammograms tended to reach relatively flat profiles after a smaller number of CV cycles compared to the NIP ones. This difference in behavior may indicate altered kinetics of polymer film growth when PFOA is present.

A plausible contributing factor could be related to interactions between *o*-PD (or its oxidized intermediates) and PFOA at the interface. In a similar system, Tricase and coworkers (Tricase et al., 2024) noticed a faster electropolymerization kinetics in the presence of the negatively charged template molecule (2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid) at pH 5.8 (when compared to the NIP), which they attributed to electrostatic interactions with positively charged *o*-PD species. Given that PFOA is predominantly deprotonated at pH 5.8 (pKa in the range between 0.5 and 3.8 (Hussain et al., 2022)) during the electropolymerization step, a similar effect could operate here. Since the electropolymerization process of *o*-PD leads to the formation of positively charged overoxidized intermediates, monomer organization at the electrode interface and growth rate of the polymeric film might be accelerated and enhanced under such conditions (Tricase et al., 2024; Losito et al., 2003a). However, in the absence of direct surface morphology studies, this should be regarded as a working hypothesis. Undoubtedly, pH also affects the resolution of the two peaks described for *o*-PD and their peak potential. Particularly, studies show a shift in peak potential toward lower values as the pH increases (Losito et al., 2003b). Nonetheless, as reported in the literature after accurate optimizations, a pH range equal to or close to that reported in this paper, namely around pH 5.8, is mostly used for *o*-PD-based MIPs (Moro et al., 2019; Karimian et al., 2018).

To further understand and demonstrate the formation of the polymeric film on the electrodes, their surface was characterized at different stages of the electrode fabrication process by recording Raman spectra and performing CVs in ammonia buffer at pH 8.4 containing 0.5 mM FcCOOH, sweeping the potential over a window from 0 V to +0.6 V at 50 mV s^{-1} . Fig. 4a and b reports the cyclic voltammograms at the bare electrodes (AuE or GCE) and once modified with the poly(*o*-PD) film, before and after template removal. A clear difference is observable

Fig. 3. Electropolymerization of *o*-PD through 25 CV scans (50 mV s^{-1}) at AuE and GCE for MIP and NIP sensors. The dashed red curve highlights the last scan. The graphs are equally scaled and plotted as J values ($\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$) as a function of E (V). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

between the voltammograms at the bare electrodes and those at the modified ones. In particular, the bare GCE shows distinct anodic and cathodic peaks around $+0.36 \text{ V}$ and $+0.28 \text{ V}$, respectively. Once the MIP layer is electropolymerized, as expected, the resulting voltammogram pre-template removal shows the complete suppression of FcCOOH-related faradaic peaks (at the GCE), indicating a complete coverage of the electrode surface with the non- or poorly conductive poly(*o*-PD) layer that hinders the diffusion of the redox mediator to the underlying electrode surface and, thus, the electron transfer processes at the electrode-electrolyte interface. Upon removing the template molecule from the MIP, the electron transfer between FcCOOH and the electrode surface is allowed. However, notable differences in the resulting voltammograms can be observed compared to those obtained at the bare surfaces. Particularly, these can be summed up with a significant decrease in the peak current densities and a worsening of the $|i_a/i_c|$ ratio. Indeed, these differences are consistent with the introduction of a resistive component potentially linked to the obstructed mass transport of the redox mediator into and out of the porous MIP layer. The re-introduction of PFOA inside the cavities upon interaction with the sample should further enhance such differences, as these will be correlated to the amount of PFOA captured by the MIP layer, as described in the following sections.

The characterization *via* Raman spectroscopy provided further insights into the structural evolution of the MIP formation on both electrodes. Raman spectra were recorded at three key fabrication stages: (i) at the bare AuE and GCE surfaces (Fig. 4c,f), (ii) at the MIP-coated AuE and GCE surfaces before template removal (Fig. 4d,g), and (iii) at the MIP-coated AuE and GCE surfaces after template extraction (20 min in methanol under stirring) (Fig. 4e,h). As expected, the bare AuE exhibited minimal Raman activity. On the other hand, the PFOA-mediated electropolymerization of *o*-PD generated a series of well-defined spectral bands. The region between 1525 and 1580 cm^{-1} reveals intense aromatic C=C stretching modes ascribable to phenyl rings. The broad,

weaker bands around 2940 and 3120 cm^{-1} might reflect N-H stretching vibrations from residual monomer moieties, absent at the bare surfaces. Notably, two distinct bands appear at approximately 1235 and 1300 cm^{-1} , consistent with C-F stretching vibrations of the PFOA entrapped within the polymer film, which potentially represents a direct spectroscopic fingerprint of successful imprinting. While maintaining the characteristic polymer-related peaks, template removal resulted in the attenuation of the signals at 1235 and 1300 cm^{-1} and the reappearance of the peaks below 1000 cm^{-1} proper of the pristine surface. This potentially indicates the efficient PFOA extraction without compromising the imprinted matrix integrity.

Raman spectra were recorded under identical conditions at the bare GCE and at the MIP-coated GCE, before and after template removal. As expected, important differences were observed on the pristine surface due to the intrinsic GCE's sp^2 carbon backbone. Its spectrum is dominated by the D band around 1350 cm^{-1} and the G band around 1598 cm^{-1} , indicative of structural disorder and in-plane sp^2 C=C stretching, respectively. Indeed, these bands complicate spectral interpretation by covering most of the information in this fingerprint region (*i.e.*, weaker C-F stretching vibrations and polymer-specific bands). In the case of the MIP-coated GCE with the template, the bands visible around 3100 cm^{-1} , which are absent on the bare GCE, might be associated to the N-H stretching within the polymer film. Moreover, the peaks at 1350 and 1598 cm^{-1} increase as a result of the polymer/PFOA coating. After template extraction, a reduction in intensity of PFOA-specific C-F modes (around 1300 cm^{-1}) is observed.

Collectively, these data and those acquired by electrochemical techniques provided a further proof of the formation of a robust MIP layer on both AuE and GCE, suggesting good efficacy of the template removal phase in methanol, and – potentially – the correct retention of the imprinted PFOA recognition sites.

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammograms in ammonia buffer pH 8.4 in the presence of 0.5 mM FcCOOH at bare (a) GCE and (b) AuE (dashed black line) and after the electropolymerization of *o*-PD, both before (light grey solid line) and after (dark grey solid line) template removal; scan rate: 50 mV s⁻¹. The graphs are plotted as *J* values (μA cm⁻²) as a function of *E* (V). Raman spectra recorded for AuE (c–e) and GCE (f–h) at different sensor fabrication stages: (c, f) at the bare AuE and GCE surfaces, (d, g) at the MIP-modified AuE and GCE surfaces before template removal, and (e, h) at the MIP-coated AuE and GCE surfaces after template extraction.

3.3. Selection of redox indicator

As PFOA is an electro-inactive molecule within the experimental conditions examined (Costa et al., 2023; Kazemi et al., 2020), the MIP-based sensing strategy developed relies on the use of a redox mediator to indirectly assess the binding. Thus, selecting an optimal redox mediator is a crucial aspect of the process. At this scope, this work explored two common redox probes, namely [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} and FcCOOH, evaluating their efficacy in the application proposed. To this end, the behavior of MIP-modified gold and glassy carbon electrodes was compared, after template removal, when working with either 5 mM [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} or 0.5 mM FcCOOH in ammonia buffer pH 8.4, both in the absence and presence of 10 nM PFOA. The cyclic voltammograms reported in Fig. 5 revealed well-defined reversible anodic and cathodic current peaks for FcCOOH at both AuE (Fig. 5a, +0.34 V and +0.28 V, respectively) and GCE (Fig. 5b, +0.35 V and +0.28 V, respectively). On the other hand, [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} exhibited poorly resolved faradaic signals under the same conditions, where the observed increased capacitive currents or incomplete charge transfers are consistent with diffusion-limited processes. The abovementioned differences in behavior might stem from electrostatic interactions between the molecules involved in this reaction. In particular, at pH 8.4 both PFOA and FcCOOH are mainly in their deprotonated forms, thus both negatively charged (Kazemi et al., 2020; Karimian et al., 2018). As reported by

Kazemi et al. (2020), in these conditions their competition within the MIP binding sites is facilitated. Indeed, as PFOA is introduced into the imprinted cavities, FcCOOH finds a more intense resistance in its access to the electrode surface, producing an enhanced signal change. On the other hand, the structural properties of FcCOOH might lead to unique behavior with respect to [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} within the experimental conditions herein examined (Rittner et al., 2024). The structure of FcCOOH combines an organometallic ferrocene core with a -COOH functional group. As such, it is characterized by a portion potentially more prone to hydrophobic interactions with the fluorocarbon chain of PFOA, while the carboxylate moiety guarantees water solubility. In this context, studies have shown that many PFAS detection and absorption strategies heavily rely on mechanisms based on combinations of electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions (Zheng et al., 2025). By contrast, the highly charged nature of [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} may face disadvantages in this sensing scheme, as it can be subjected to even stronger electrostatic repulsion with PFOA molecules, not supported by the presence of hydrophobic moieties that could interact with the fluorocarbon backbone of PFOA. In addition, it has to be considered the difference in dimension of the two molecules; FcCOOH, with its smaller hydrodynamic radius together with the abovementioned superior lipophilic character, can afford a more facile diffusion through the porous MIP structure with respect to [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} (Lu et al., 2022). All these considerations confirm the importance of synergistic electrostatic-hydrophobic interactions for

Fig. 5. Cyclic voltammograms with 0.5 mM FcCOOH (dashed lines) and 5 mM $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$ (solid lines) in ammonia buffer pH 8.4 registered at AuE (a) and GCE (b) modified with the MIP layer after template removal. The graphs are equally scaled and plotted as J values ($\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$) as a function of E (V). Optimization of (c) extraction solution for the template removal phase, (d) rebinding time in the presence of 100 nM PFOA, and (e) electrochemical technique for the detection of 10 nM PFOA. The results are expressed as (c) J_p % variations in the absence of PFOA, (d) J_p change (%), or (e) normalized ΔJ_p values.

signal generation when dealing with PFAS (Guo et al., 2024).

3.4. Optimizations on MIP preparation and PFOA detection

Before assessing the overall analytical performances of the sensors, a study was conducted to investigate the best conditions to run the analysis, evaluating rebinding durations, optimal electrochemical technique, and strategies for the synthesis of the MIP layer. Regarding the synthesis of the poly(*o*-PD) layer, the literature already presents several studies that have optimized all the crucial parameters that are critical when approaching the detection of PFAS, including PFOS and PFOA. Particularly, the most important aspects to consider are (i) the number of CV scans to obtain a stable film, which is also linked to its thickness, (ii) the pH of the electrolyte in which the electropolymerization is performed, (iii) the monomer:template molar ratio, (iv) the time and solvent mixture used for template removal, and (v) the rebinding time and the electrolyte when interacting with the analyte. For instance, studying MIPs based on *o*-PD, Karimian and colleagues (Karimian et al., 2018) found that 25 cycles in the range from 0.0 to +1.0 V (vs. Ag/AgCl, 1 M KCl) in 0.1 M acetate buffer (pH 5.8), with a monomer:template molar ratio of 10:1, a rebinding time of 15 min in 0.01 M ammonia buffer (pH 8.4), and a template extraction time of 20 min under mild stirring in 1:1 v/v methanol:H₂O, worked better than the other conditions tested for the detection of PFOS. Working in similar conditions, the same optimizations were also described by Lu et al. (2022). Working on the detection of PFOA with *o*-PD-based MIPs, Wei and coworkers (Wei et al., 2023) registered the maximum sensor response again after 25 CV cycles (0.0–1.0 V, 10:1 monomer:template ratio, 2:1 v/v acetate buffer:methanol, pH 5.8), stating that a lower number of cycles would lead to thinner films and only partial coverage of the electrode surface, whereas more cycles would produce thicker films which result in poorer accessibility to the recognition sites. Likewise, they also found that after 15 min of incubation, the sensor response reaches a plateau, a sign of the

formation of suitable imprinted cavities, while longer rebinding times led to the desorption of PFOA molecules from the MIP's cavities. Moreover, they observed that 15 min under stirring in 1:1 v/v methanol:H₂O were enough to remove the template molecule from the MIP layer.

The abovementioned conditions reported in the literature were tested to verify their coherence and validity within our experimental setup. As indicated in the Materials and Methods section, optimal results were registered upon synthesizing a poly(*o*-PD) film by sweeping the potential 25 times from 0.0 V to +1.0 V in CV at the scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹ in a 2:1 v/v solution of acetate buffer (pH 5.8) and methanol containing a monomer:template ratio of 10:1. Nonetheless, different template removal optimal conditions were experimentally observed compared to those usually exploited in literature-reported works. Indeed, this phase critically impacts the final performances of the sensor as it determines cavity accessibility upon PFOA rebinding. Three extraction solutions were tested to remove PFOA from the poly(*o*-PD) film: (i) pure methanol, (ii) 1:1 v/v methanol:water, and (iii) 1:2 v/v methanol:water. This step was followed by registering the current peak density of 0.5 mM FcCOOH on the MIP-modified electrode. As reported in Fig. 5c, pure methanol proved to be more efficient under these conditions, resulting in a signal >5-fold greater than the 1:1 v/v methanol:water mixture and >30-fold higher with respect to the 1:2 v/v counterpart. Considering the high log K_{ow} value of 4.67 for PFOA, as reported by Xiang et al. (2018), these findings align with the superior efficacy of methanol in displacing PFOA without the added content of water that increases the overall solvent polarity. This latter effect in the co-presence of water might lead to slightly reduced solubility of PFOA, thus accentuating its retention within the MIP cavities. Subsequent experiments were thus conducted by removing the template molecules under stirring for 20 min in methanol. Interestingly, most other literature-reported works focused on PFOS detection (instead of PFOA) achieve optimal template removals using 1:1 v/v methanol:water media, suggesting that PFAS-specific solvent optimizations are

necessary even when these fluorinated compounds are similar in structure.

As an additional optimization experiment, Fig. 5d reports the study of the interaction time between PFOA and the sensor. Changes in signal obtained in the presence of 100 nM PFOA after an incubation time of 5, 15, 30, 60 min, and 17 h were evaluated. The bars in Fig. 5d show the signal decrease as the sensor interacts with PFOA, indicating a good response of the sensor to the analyte of interest. After 5 min, an important J_p reduction is already observable. This signal decline is enhanced upon studying longer interaction times, reaching a plateau after 15 min as slightly longer times seem to produce negligible effects. On the other hand, when leaving the electrode submerged overnight (17 h) inside the PFOA-containing sample, an increase in J_p is observed, sign of a partial desorption of PFOA from the MIP layer. After these considerations and to balance analysis duration and sensitivity, the optimized rebinding time was defined to be of 15 min.

Another aspect that was evaluated for the optimization of the procedure was to choose the most suitable electrochemical technique for PFOA detection. Most works reported in the literature are found to exploit DPV for this specific application. However, other pulse methods designed to enhance faradaic response against background currents and widely exploited in trace electrochemical analyses exist. Thus, initial method optimizations investigated an additional technique, namely SWV, comparing its performances with those of DPV by working in identical experimental conditions, namely in 0.5 mM FcCOOH (in ammonia buffer pH 8.4). The technique-related parameters applied are reported in the Materials and Methods section. Fig. 5e demonstrates that the signal variation, expressed as $\Delta J_p/J_{p0}$ %, obtained via DPV and SWV at the GCE after interacting with 10 nM PFOA does not differ

significantly. These similar performances might be linked to effects that limit the kinetic advantages typically associated with SWV (e.g., better discrimination against capacitive currents). Examples of such phenomena can include those related to the hampered charge transfer processes caused by the non-conductive poly(*o*-PD) film, which restricts the benefits only to the surface-bound FcCOOH molecules able to access the electrode surface. Thus, both pulsed techniques might offer similar performances under such diffusion-limited or surface-constrained conditions, where more complex scenarios can occur (Olmos et al., 2015). In light of these comparable performances and the wider application of DPV with MIP-based sensors for PFAS detection in the literature, subsequent experiments were carried out using DPV.

3.5. Analytical performance

After implementing the optimization measures, the next step consisted in the evaluation of the analytical performance of the two sensors for PFOA determination. DPV scans were carried out consecutively on the same sensor following stepwise increases in PFOA concentration within the incubation solution (ammonia buffer, pH 8.4) and a 15-min equilibration time under mild magnetic stirring, in line with other sequential-exposure workflows reported in the literature for PFAS sensing (Kazemi et al., 2020). Fig. 6a shows the normalized ΔJ_p values plotted versus PFOA concentration on a semi-logarithmic scale. The data were fitted to the Langmuir-Freundlich isotherm model to study the binding interaction between the MIP-modified AuE and GCE with PFOA, accounting for the potential heterogeneous binding site distributions and the non-ideal adsorption behavior. Notably, similar saturation levels were found for both electrodes, with maximum normalized response

Fig. 6. (a) Calibration curves: increasing PFOA concentrations were added at the AuE and GCE modified with the MIP layer. Normalized J_p % values are plotted as a function of PFOA concentration on a logarithmic scale. Grey shaded areas indicate the 95 % confidence bands. (b) Study of interferents: SNR change (%) of 0 nM PFOA (blank) and 10 nM PFOA both alone and in the co-presence of equimolar concentrations (10 nM) of potential interferents (amoxicillin, Pb^{2+} , hydroquinone, Aroclor 1242) in ammonia buffer pH 8.4 at the MIP-modified GCE. The grey area underlines the mean SNR change ($n = 3$) obtained with 10 nM PFOA alone \pm its standard deviation. (c) Spiked buffer or filtered/unfiltered wastewater effluent samples; the bars show $\Delta J_p/J_{p0}$ % values, whereas the blue squares indicate matrix effect values. The blue area highlights the $\pm 20\%$ tolerance window around the ideal ME% value of 100 %. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

values of $96.5 \pm 4.2\%$ for the AuE and $98.0 \pm 5.2\%$ for the GCE, displaying comparable dynamic ranges within the experimental conditions examined. Likewise, the heterogeneity indexes obtained from the Langmuir-Freundlich model differed slightly, reaching values of 0.62 ± 0.09 and 0.50 ± 0.11 for the AuE and the GCE, respectively. These values, lower than unity, indicate site heterogeneity, as often observed for MIP-based platforms given the distribution of imprinted cavities with varying affinities and local conditions. This site heterogeneity was further corroborated by Scatchard analysis, observing deviation from the linearity expected for a homogeneous Langmuir model (*data not shown*). This non-linear trend in the Scatchard plot supports the hypothesis of a multi-site binding mechanism, potentially involving sites with different accessibility (Pesavento et al., 2019). As described by K. D. Shimizu (2002), this behavior is common in MIP-based systems and complicates the comparison of the binding properties between the two MIP-modified electrodes.

Similarities in the abovementioned parameters also reflected on analytical performance. In the case of the GCE, a limit of detection of 48.7 pM (corresponding to 20.2 ppt of PFOA) and a LOQ of 89.3 pM (37.0 ppt) were calculated from the calibration curve. The gold electrode exhibited a comparable LOD of 55.5 pM (23.0 ppt) and a LOQ of 118.0 pM (48.9 ppt). Notably, these detection limits are below the threshold of 100 ppt established for the “Sum of PFAS” in drinking water in Europe (Official Journal of the European Union, 2020). Furthermore, subtle differences were noticed in the midpoint concentration values (C_{50}), defined as the concentration of PFOA required to obtain 50 % of the maximum response. Particularly, C_{50} values of 2.74 nM and 0.67 nM were noted for the AuE and the GCE, respectively, indicating that the GCE requires a marginally lower concentration of PFOA to reach half of its maximum response and, consequently, suggesting a slightly more efficient interaction in the low concentration range.

The method's reproducibility was also evaluated. Particularly, two types of relative standard deviations (RSD) were calculated: (i) an intra-electrode RSD value, referring to repeated measurements carried out on the same electrode after multiple analyte removals (reusability), and (ii) an inter-electrode RSD value, considering measurements performed on different electrodes in different days, thus accounting for fabrication variability. The intra-electrode RSD was found to be 16.5 % ($n = 3$), while the inter-electrode one was 3.3 % ($n = 3$). It is interesting to observe that the inter-electrode reproducibility was lower than the intra-electrode one, suggesting that repeated sensor regenerations (through analyte removals in methanol) affected the reproducibility more than fabrication inconsistencies between different freshly prepared sensors. This high variability could be attributed to the cumulative structural alterations to the poly(*o*-PD) film and the potential gradual loss of its adhesion to the electrode surface during the repeated methanol-mediated template extractions (Liu et al., 2025a; Zidarić et al., 2023). In other words, while the inter-electrode reproducibility confirms a repeatable fabrication protocol, the intra-electrode data highlight limitations in sensor reusability under the current regeneration conditions. Although aggressive analyte removal can offer better analytical performances in a single use, future work could explore mitigation strategies that optimize solvent exposure to extend sensor reusability over time.

Overall, it can be concluded that comparable analytical performances and sensitivities were achieved with the two MIP-modified electrodes, AuE and GCE, despite the differences evidenced through the electrochemical characterization. Probably, as previously mentioned, the poly(*o*-PD) layer partially decouples sensor response from the underlying substrate's intrinsic electrochemical properties, restricting electron transfer kinetics only to surface-proximal FcCOOH molecules able to penetrate the polymeric film, thus reducing contributions from the electrode's bulk electroactive area. These findings may suggest researchers to prioritize other practical aspects (e.g., overall cost, durability, availability and sustainability of materials, etc.) when designing a MIP-based sensor for these fluorinated contaminants.

3.6. Effect of potential interferents

The specificity of the MIP-based sensor towards PFOA was tested by performing measurements in the co-presence of other chemical species often encountered in water samples and able to potentially interfere with the detection of PFOA. Indeed, while MIPs' cavities are designed for specific recognition, non-specific adsorption remains a known limitation that can influence sensor accuracy, especially in complex matrices (Karrat and Amine, 2024). The selection of the interfering molecules to be studied was based on their environmental relevance, common co-occurrence with PFAS, and distinct chemical properties that could potentially challenge the sensor's analytical and electrochemical behavior (Reynoso et al., 2024). Specifically, tests were carried out with: (i) amoxicillin (AMX), a β -lactam antibiotic included in EU watch lists, chosen as a model antibiotic and pharmaceutical contaminant, given that their contamination of water bodies is increasingly concerning (Yashir et al., 2025; Fabregat-Safont et al., 2021); (ii) Pb^{2+} , a heavy metal that is among the most commonly monitored pollutants in water (Laschi et al., 2024; Palchetti et al., 2000), also selected to study the interference of positive ions potentially able to electrostatically interact with the poly(*o*-PD)-modified surface; (iii) hydroquinone (HQ), a redox-active phenolic compound widely used in cosmetics and other industrial applications, whose electroactive nature might interfere with the redox signal of FcCOOH in a signal-off readout mechanism (Shanbhag et al., 2024; Verrucchi et al., 2023; Berti et al., 2009); and (iv) Aroclor 1242, a commercial mixture of polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) containing approximately 42 % chlorine by weight, selected to evaluate the co-presence of other highly hazardous and persistent organic pollutants (De Rosa et al., 2022).

The study consisted in exposing the MIP-modified electrodes to 10 nM PFOA in ammonia buffer pH 8.4, both alone and in the equimolar co-presence of the abovementioned potential interfering molecules (Clark and Dick, 2020). Each interferent was evaluated with a freshly prepared sensor. The signal reduction was quantified as the percentage of signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) changes with respect to the blank (buffer alone, 0 nM PFOA and 0 nM interferents). Fig. 6b shows a comparison of the results. First, a baseline SNR in the absence of any analyte or interferent (blank) was registered, followed by the characteristic signal reduction in the presence of PFOA. In the equimolar co-presence of AMX and Pb^{2+} , small reductions in SNR change of approximately 5.8 % and 3.3 %, respectively, from the PFOA sample were observed, suggesting minor interfering capabilities. On the other hand, a more pronounced reduction in the SNR change was found in the co-presence of HQ and Aroclor (−14.6 % and −11.3 %, respectively, with respect to the signal for the PFOA sample), showing less reproducible results. These results indicate that these molecules may challenge to varying degrees the selectivity of the sensor for PFOA, suggesting that robust sample treatment procedures might be required to mitigate their interference when analyzing complex real-world matrices such as wastewater. Another relevant aspect is the sensor's selectivity against other structurally related PFAS. Indeed, their cross-reactivity represents a well-documented limitation of MIP sensors in this field and several works report on significant or similar affinities for multiple PFAS compounds (Wang et al., 2021). As described by Kazemi et al. (2020) and others (Tabar et al., 2025), MIP sensors exhibit similar binding affinities for PFAS compounds such as PFOA, PFOS, perfluorobutanoic acid (PFBA), perfluorobutanesulfonic acid (PFBS), and others due to overlapping cavity sizes and chemical functionalities, which indeed limit the ability to distinguish individual perfluorinated congeners from complex mixtures. This further suggests that cross-reactivity among PFAS is inherent to the approach and must be addressed through additional optimizations of the fabrication conditions and optimal sample treatments, which are subjects of ongoing research. On the other hand, this cross-reactivity aligns with regulatory requirements (e.g., under the EU Directive, 2020/2184) that establish limits for mixtures of PFAS (e.g., “Total PFAS” and “Sum of PFAS”, as mentioned in the Introduction

section) rather than individual compounds thresholds. As recently highlighted by Tabar and co-workers (Tabar et al., 2025), these limits recognize that environmental monitoring could benefit from detecting multiple PFAS simultaneously when PFAS co-occur in contaminated matrices. Pitruzzella et al. (2024) explicitly leveraged this aspect to design a MIP-based system that responds to the total sum of PFAS present in the sample in the range from C4 to C12 (with the highest response from C8 analogs, like PFOS and PFOA), demonstrating that such broad-spectrum detection can be advantageous for regulatory compliance screening.

3.7. Evaluation of sensor behavior in wastewater

After testing the sensor in standard buffer solutions, the in-matrix practical applicability was evaluated by examining the sensor's behavior in real samples, assessing the effect of a complex matrix under controlled spiking. Wastewater samples from a local municipal treatment plant were analyzed, considering both the raw influent (pre-treatments) and the effluent (post-treatments) samples. The plant treats a mix of domestic and industrial influent streams, and its treated effluent is reintroduced into the natural water body, making its PFAS content critical under environmental and regulatory standpoints.

Before the analyses, wastewater samples were added of small volumes of 0.3 M ammonia buffer and their pH was adjusted to 8.4. Influent and effluent samples were analyzed both as received and after a filtration step through a 0.45 μm PES membrane to remove impurities and particulate matter. Notably, PES was chosen to run the filtration as its suitability for PFAS analysis was recently demonstrated (Lozeau et al.; Noda Morishita et al., 2025). Freshly prepared MIP-modified GCEs were used for each sample analyzed. Given the comparable sensitivities demonstrated in buffer between AuE and GCE, the latter was chosen as support for real sample analysis since it requires a more streamlined preparation protocol, which needs a less demanding mechanical polishing and does not include electrochemical activation in sulfuric acid.

Preliminary analyses were conducted studying the raw influent, both as unfiltered and after filtration; however, highly variable signals across repeated measurements (RSD >20 %) and rapid signal saturation were observed, rendering these data unreliable (*data not shown*). This phenomenon was attributed to a complex matrix effect (ME% values > 120 % were observed over a concentration range between 0.1 and 1 nM PFOA, *data not shown*) given by the high concentration of suspended solids and possible competing interferents, which collectively overwhelm the MIP's finite binding capacity or result in non-specific adsorption events that may interfere with subsequent FcCOOH diffusion and redox behavior. Other works report similar results in the analysis of real surface water samples (Hafeez et al., 2024). Indeed, this preliminary exploration provided insights into the challenges of analyzing untreated wastewater, suggesting that sample dilution or further pre-concentration protocols, more complex filtrations, or other sample pre-treatments might be required to analyze raw wastewater influent streams.

Subsequent efforts were focused on the effluent, the most critical sample in terms of compliance with safety thresholds by regulatory bodies. Once again, the effluent was analyzed both before and after filtration through the 0.45 μm PES membrane. Fig. 6c shows the $\Delta J_p/J_{p0}$ % responses and the matrix effect values upon allowing the sensor to interact with either buffer solution (ammonia buffer pH 8.4), filtered effluent, and unfiltered effluent after spiking the samples with PFOA covering a range of concentrations typically found on average in wastewater bodies worldwide under varying conditions (Moneta et al., 2023; Bothfeld and Mathieu, 2022; Kurwadkar et al., 2022). Particularly, PFOA concentrations of 0.1 nM (41.4 ppt), 0.5 nM (207.1 ppt), and 1 nM (414.1 ppt) were tested. While no uniform regulatory limits currently exist across Europe regarding PFAS levels in wastewater, local authorities have started setting emission thresholds to safeguard surface water bodies. In this context, the abovementioned PFOA concentrations

tested align with both the most stringent EU threshold for drinking water (0.1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, 100 ppt) and local provisional discharge limits for treated wastewater, as those in Italy of 0.3 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (300 ppt) set by the Piedmont Region (Regional Law n. 25/2021 and the Decree of the Regional Government n. 60–5220/2022) and of 0.5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (500 ppt) imposed by the Region of Veneto (Decree n. 16/2020 of the Region's Official Gazette).

Measurements in the unfiltered effluent revealed strong and immediate signal saturation, indicating that interfering matter in the raw matrix may non-specifically occupy the MIP cavities or greatly influence the subsequent electrochemical behavior of the redox probe. As a result, the $\Delta J_p/J_{p0}$ % remained nearly constant across all three concentrations tested, with ME% values that reflected this trend. These results indicate that, while molecular recognition fidelity might be maintained, the strong matrix interference still present in the unfiltered effluent masks concentration-dependent responses, hampering quantitative determination of PFOA. Thus, as previously mentioned, a filtration step was introduced in the attempt to mitigate this phenomenon. After filtration, the effluent exhibited concentration-dependent $\Delta J_p/J_{p0}$ % values substantially closer to those observed in buffer. Consequently, all ME % values at the three PFOA concentrations tested fell within the ± 20 % tolerance window (from the ideal 100 % value, which represents a negligible matrix effect) commonly accepted without the need for any further optimization (Stahnke et al., 2012), with an average value of (95 \pm 10) % across all concentrations. These results suggest that a simple filtration step significantly improves matrix compatibility, reducing interfering residual effects and restoring the conditions under which the sensor can be applied to the detection of PFOA without the need for additional sample manipulation, even at PFOA concentrations below the thresholds reported by European guidelines. Indeed, while adding a preprocessing step, this filtration – which could be integrated into automated sampling systems – can be applied to small sample volumes and remains quicker than common cleanup procedures required for hyphenated chromatographic strategies (van Leeuwen and de Boer, 2007; Liu et al., 2025b).

Notably, once the MIP-based sensing platform is prepared, its deployment only involves a straightforward procedure that consists in the immersion of the sensor in the (filtered) sample for a short period of time followed by electrochemical measurement in a FcCOOH-containing solution using a portable potentiostat, many of which are now smartphone-compatible. Overall, these findings demonstrate potential for PFOA detection, focusing on sensor behavior in a complex matrix such as wastewater. Nonetheless, the approach is not intended to replace quantitative laboratory-based methods, but might work as a practical and accessible solution in support of them for rapid screenings directly at the wastewater treatment site, especially considering that the few commercial kits currently available require laboratory confirmation (Menger et al., 2021).

4. Conclusions

This work developed and optimized an electrochemical sensor based on poly(*o*-PD) MIPs for the detection of PFOA in wastewater. Analytical performances were assessed across electrode materials, redox mediators, experimental conditions, and environmental matrices, explicitly testing whether substrate-driven electrochemistry substantially persists once the *o*-PD layer governs the interface. Template extraction and substrate-dependent polymer morphologies were studied *via* cyclic voltammetry and Raman spectroscopy. Optimizations in the experimental conditions were introduced, focusing especially on MIP preparation and electrochemical readout. The electrochemical characterization showed kinetic advantages of the AuE over the GCE, yet the two MIP-modified platforms converged to comparable detection limits upon detecting PFOA in spiked buffer solution. Notably, sensitivities and dynamic ranges that fall within the concentration window relevant to current European regulations were met without resorting to substrate-specific enhancements. Signal variability accumulated upon repeated use of the sensors

and template extractions highlighted that integrity and regeneration of the imprinted film influence sensor's practical applicability more than electrode surface identity. The optimized setup was challenged in the analysis of real samples collected from a wastewater treatment plant, focusing both on the raw influent and the effluent, before and after a simple filtration step through a 0.45 µm PES membrane. Matrix-induced signal saturation and high variability was observed for influent and/or unfiltered samples, suggesting the need for more complex sample pre-treatment strategies to analyze raw wastewater. Contrarily, consistent responses and acceptable matrix effects were found in the analysis of the filtered effluent, the most critical stream for compliance checks and routine screening. This work provided insights into the interdependencies governing PFOA sensing, electron transfer kinetics, and other factors able to influence the analysis, highlighting the complexity behind the analytical translation from standard solutions to real-world scenarios. Moreover, these findings support a design perspective in which optimizations of the recognition layer (e.g., monomer chemistry, monomer:template ratio, extraction protocols, etc.) should be prioritized over complex and time-consuming electrode surface engineering when regulatory-range detection is already reached with well-formed MIPs on canonical bare electrodes.

These results show that the proposed sensor and approach could represent a promising solution for rapid large-scale on-site monitoring of PFOA, especially as a more practical screening device that supports and complements traditional LC-MS/MS-based methodologies. Future efforts will prioritize improving sensor stability and reusability, expanding selectivity against similar PFAS congeners, developing automatable protocols for online decentralized analyses, and conducting external validation against reference methods in wastewater.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Patrick Severin Sfragano: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Anna Emanuele:** Investigation, Data curation. **Serena Laschi:** Writing – original draft. **Giovanni Ferraro:** Investigation. **Emiliano Fratini:** Investigation. **Ilaria Palchetti:** Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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